

Exploring Airlines Scheduled Buffer Time Adjustment Strategies: An Analytical Approach

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Abstract—Airlines add buffer times in schedules to absorb the impacts of stochastic disruptions and improve on-time performance. However, it remains unclear whether and how their buffer-setting strategies effectively mitigate delays or, in some cases, worsen on-time performance. To this end, we develop an analytical approach to quantitatively capture the trade-off between buffer time and delay in the schedule adjustment process. We also define 12 buffer adjustment scenarios, enabling the analysis of effectiveness. Using an open-source dataset, the proposed methods were applied to empirical studies on five U.S. airlines. Results suggest that buffer adjustments for around 31%-38% of the flights are ineffective in these airlines from a retrospective view. Alternatively, it highlights the potential improvements that could be made if airlines consider future delay variations in schedule adjustments. Also, we find that airlines tend to make minor adjustments in buffer, which limits their adaptability to system changes. We employ the Multinomial Logit Model to identify contributing factors of ineffective buffer adjustments. Empirical evidence suggests that tailored adjustment strategies are needed for flights with low frequency, small true delay variation, and long flight time to enhance effectiveness. This research offers theoretical insights and practical tools to enhance airlines' schedule adjustment strategies.

Keywords—airline scheduling; flight buffer; trade-off strategy; analytical approach; empirical study

I. INTRODUCTION

The schedule setting by airlines serves as the cornerstone of air transportation system operations, shaping the spatial-temporal distribution of traffic and allocation of resources. A critical component in the flight schedule is Scheduled Block Time (SBT). SBT is defined as the duration between scheduled departure and scheduled arrival time in the computer reservation system [1]. Typically, airlines set the SBTs for flights six months in advance and regularly update them to respond to evolving operating conditions and airlines' business strategy [2].

However, flight times are usually subject to many sources of variability in actual operations. This can lead to flight delays, the propagation of delays throughout the network, reduced punctuality, and increased operational costs. There are two primary approaches to addressing delays. From the perspective of airspace managers, solutions focus on air traffic flow management (ATFM), which is on the pre-tactical level.

From the perspective of airspace users, i.e. airlines, flight delays and on-time performance (OTP) hold significant importance. With the implementation of the On-Time Disclosure Rule, OTP has become a critical factor influencing consumer decisions, alongside ticket fares [3]. This incentivizes airlines to add buffer time in the schedule to absorb impacts of stochastic disruptions and improve schedule reliability, which is on the strategic level. This practice is also called schedule padding. Since delays are measured against schedule, airlines can manipulate their reported OTP by adjusting buffer time.

Flight buffer times refer to the extra time padded to the unimpeded flight time under ideal operation conditions [4]. The amount of buffer in flight schedule reflects airlines' longer-term expectations of delays and strategies to cope with flight time volatility [5], which is closely related to the predictability performance in the National Airspace System (NAS). Changes in buffer time are primarily driven by operational performance. Poor OTP usually leads to increased SBTs in the next year [6]. However, setting longer buffer times is not always the optimal solution. The buffer time longer than necessary will reduce the utilization rate of aircraft, and increase payment to crews as it is determined by the SBT [1]. Additionally, under favorable traffic conditions, extended buffer times can lead to an increase in early-arriving flights, potentially causing gate unavailability and resulting in ramp congestion [7]. Therefore, both flight delays and buffer times are critical cost drivers for airlines [8]. This underscores the importance of the trade-off between improving OTP and the cost of longer scheduled times in airlines' flight schedule settings.

Research on airline scheduling can be broadly categorized into three areas. The first focuses on developing robust schedules through optimization techniques, aiming to enhance schedule robustness against operational uncertainties [9] [10]. The second examines the impact of buffer times on delays and delay propagation. Brueckner et al. analyzed an airline's choice of flight buffers and ground buffers using a simple two-flight model, taking passenger disutilities from lateness and earliness into account along with buffer costs [11]. Kafle and Zou developed an analytical-econometric approach to quantify propagated and newly formed delays from different ways that delays are absorbed by the buffer [12]. The third

develops schedule-setting models that consider determinant factors, historical performance, and market data. Wang et al. developed econometric models to compare the differences in SBT-setting behavior between major airlines in China and the U.S. [7]. They found that the inter-country differences in SBT-setting behavior fully explain the difference in OTP between the two countries. The above research considered the SBT setting in a static context. Very few studies investigate SBT adjustment in response to historical performance. Hao and Hansen developed regression models to analyze the impacts of on-time and early arrivals on SBT adjustment [6]. Kang and Hansen applied discrete choice models to investigate airlines' preferences in SBT adjustment [2]. They found that both OTP and early arrival are important to airlines, but the former is considerably more valuable.

However, the aforementioned studies primarily focus on modeling the scheduling strategies and predicting the SBT or its adjustment value directly using historical data. They do not examine whether these strategies are appropriate. Specifically, it remains unclear whether the current setting strategy effectively responds to changes in flight delays caused by operational environment shifts. Does the flight buffer time truly achieve its intended goal of offsetting flight delays, or does it, in some cases, deteriorate on-time performance? For which OD pairs is the buffer time setting ineffective, and what are the driving factors? Addressing these questions will provide valuable insights to enhance airlines' buffer-setting strategies and improve overall operational performance.

To bridge the gap, in this study, we develop an analytical approach aimed at analyzing the trade-off between buffer time and delay in flight schedule adjustment. Through flight time decomposition, we identified that this strategy can be interpreted as a decision regarding how much of the delay is hidden within the schedule and how much is exposed in the observed performance. By analyzing the quantitative relationship between changes in buffer and arrival delay, we integrated them into one equation to quantitatively capture the dynamics of this trade-off. Then the proposed model is applied to conduct an empirical study on five U.S. airlines. We examined common and distinct patterns in buffer adjustments between full-service carriers (FSCs) and low-cost carriers (LCCs) and analyzed the efficiency of their buffer time settings.

This study contributes to the literature and industry in the following ways: (1) We develop a unified model to capture the quantitative relationship between scheduled buffer adjustment and arrival delay in the trade-off behavior. (2) We defined 12 buffer adjustment scenarios with detailed interpretations based on the proposed model. It provides a tool to analyze whether the buffer adjustment decisions are appropriate or not. (3) Our model does not require access to sensitive information such as an airline's cost factors and business strategy. Without estimating by historical data, it is also adaptable to significant changes in the operation environment. (4) We identify characteristics of flights with ineffective buffer adjustment. This study provides a foundational approach to investigating airlines' trade-off strategies between buffer adjustment and delay. We can apply the proposed method to infer airlines'

responses to changes in future operational conditions in the NAS, such as improvements contributed by NEXTGEN, and then further assess their consequences.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II introduces the definitions and calculations of buffer time and flight delay. Section III describes the proposed analytical approach and discusses its potential applications and advantages. Section IV presents the empirical analysis results and investigates the driving factors of ineffective buffer adjustments. Section V concludes with key insights and directions for future work.

II. BUFFER AND DELAY CALCULATION

This section defines the homogeneous flight group to identify comparable flights across years for buffer adjustment modeling and analysis. Then, we introduce the definitions and calculation methods of three key concepts used in this paper: scheduled buffer time, observed arrival delays, and true arrival delays.

A. Identify Homogeneous Flight Groups

The Homogeneous Flight Groups (HFG) [7] is defined to identify comparable flights across years. The non-stop individual flights are aggregated by airlines, years, quarters, origin-destination pairs, and departure time windows. We divided each day into five time periods: (1) 8:00–11:59, (2) 12:00–15:59, (3) 16:00–19:59, (4) 20:00–23:59, and (5) 00:00–7:59 of the following day. The departure time window indicates the time period in which the scheduled departure time falls. For example, "UA_19_1_SFO_EWR_2" represents the group of United Airlines flights operated in the first quarter of 2019 from SFO to EWR with scheduled departure times between 12:00 and 15:59. These aggregation criteria are chosen considering the industry practice. First, each airline is responsible for its own flight schedule setting, and usually updates the schedule every 3 months. Second, on the majority of routes, airlines use almost constant buffer times across all flights on a given route [4]. For airlines having different practices, these aggregation criteria can also be adapted. Rather than directly tracking flight numbers, the HFG method does not require airlines to maintain the same flight numbering from one time period to the next. Each HFG is referred to as an individual flight f in this paper.

After identifying the HFGs, we need to determine which flight groups will be included in the analysis. If we only consider the groups with a large number of flights, only OD pairs with frequent flights will be included. If the flight number is too low, we will not have enough data to calculate the percentiles for UBT estimation. By analyzing the cumulative distribution function (CDF) plot, We set a threshold of 30 flights to select HFGs, which finally filtered out 20% of HFGs with low frequencies.

B. Buffer Time and Delay Calculation

By decomposing flight times, Figure 1 illustrates the scheduled flight times, actual flight times, scheduled buffer, flight delays, and their relationships. Accordingly, the three critical

concepts in this paper can be defined and calculated as follows:

Figure 1: Flight Time Decomposition, adapted from [4]

- a) **Scheduled flight buffer time (SFB)**: The exact amount of buffer is unknown directly according to the data. Scheduled flight buffer time is defined as the extra time padded to the unimpeded block time (UBT) in a flight schedule [4]. So, we first use a low percentile of historical actual gate-to-gate time in each HFG as the UBT. As demonstrated in previous research [12], using a low percentile rather than the absolute minimum value is more robust to measurement error and reduces the influence of the strong tailwind. The UBT of flight f in year y can be calculated as:

$$UBT_f^y = UTO_f^y + UAT_f^y + UTI_f^y \quad (1)$$

where UTO_f^y , UAT_f^y , and UTI_f^y are the unimpeded taxi-out time, unimpeded airborne time, and unimpeded taxi-in time, represented by the 5th percentile of historical actual taxi-out time, actual airborne time and actual taxi-in time, respectively. The inter-quartile range (IQR), first quartile (Q_1), and third quartile (Q_3) are applied to filter outliers. The values below $Q_1 - 1.5 \cdot IQR$ and above $Q_3 + 1.5 \cdot IQR$ are excluded before calculating the percentiles. Then, the scheduled buffer is defined as the difference between SBT and UBT, i.e.:

$$SFB_f^y = SBT_f^y - UBT_f^y \quad (2)$$

- b) **Observed arrival delay (OAD)**: Arrival delay is a critical metric to calculate on-time performance indicator [7]. To distinguish, in this study, we refer to the arrival delay as observed delay, denoted as OAD_f^y . It emphasizes that this represents the observable portion of the true arrival delay, which will be introduced later. In contrast, SFB_f^y corresponds to the unobservable portion, which can be interpreted as the part of the true arrival delay that is deliberately hidden in the schedule. The observed delay

is the difference between the actual gate arrival time (ATA) and the scheduled gate arrival time (STA). The negative value indicates an early arrival.

$$OAD_f^y = ATA_f^y - STA_f^y \quad (3)$$

- c) **True arrival delay (TAD)**: Although the observed arrival delay is the most commonly used delay metric, it does not reflect the true extent of a flight's delay. Because airlines can manipulate their punctuality by adjusting SBTs. To estimate the delay without the influence of schedule, true arrival delay TAD_f^y is applied in the analysis. According to Figure 1, it is defined as the difference between ATA and the no-delay gate arrival time under UBT. It can be calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned} TAD_f^y &= (ATA_f^y - STA_f^y) + (SBT_f^y - UBT_f^y) \\ &= OAD_f^y + SFB_f^y \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

For each HFG f , its corresponding SBT, scheduled buffer time, and observed arrival delay are represented by the median values within the group.

III. MODELING THE TRADE-OFF IN BUFFER TIME ADJUSTMENT

This section presents methods for modeling and evaluating airlines' schedule adjustment strategies. We propose a novel analytical model to quantitatively characterize the trade-off relationship between buffer time adjustment and observed delay. This adjustment trade-off model is applied to individual flights (HFG) for microscopic analysis. Then, we define 12 adjustment scenarios for analyzing buffer adjustment effectiveness. We also discuss how the proposed method supports decision-making in buffer adjustments and highlight its advantages over existing schedule-setting models.

A. Actual and Reference Adjustment Rate

In the analytical approach, we use the "rate of change" to measure the adjustment of scheduled buffer and delay. Unlike absolute change values, e.g. ΔSBT , which are widely used in the literature, the rate of change provides a relative measure of variation by accounting for the previous year's value as a baseline. It captures the proportional magnitude of change rather than just the raw difference. This normalized measure of changes allows for better comparability across different contexts, making it easier to identify trends and assess the effectiveness of adjustments.

In general cases, both buffer time and observed delay will undergo changes in the next year. Let ν_f and ω_f denote the actual change rate of observed arrival delay and scheduled buffer time, respectively. Then, the following equation holds:

$$SFB_f^{y+1} = SFB_f^y (1 + \omega_f) \quad (5)$$

$$OAD_f^{y+1} = OAD_f^y (1 + \nu_f) \quad (6)$$

For $SFB_f^y > 0$ and $OAD_f^y > 0$, $\omega_f > 0$ and $\nu_f > 0$ represent buffer and observed delay increase, while $\omega_f < 0$ and $\nu_f < 0$ represent buffer and observed delay decrease. For $OAD_f^y < 0$, $\nu_f > 0$ represent observed delay decrease, while $\nu_f < 0$ represent observed delay increase. Combining

equation (4), the change in true arrival delay can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta TAD_f &= TAD_f^{y+1} - TAD_f^y \\ &= OAD_f^y \nu_f + SFB_f^y \omega_f\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

To facilitate the understanding and quantifying the trade-off in scheduled buffer adjustment, we also define two reference conditions:

a) **Reference 1: Fix buffer.** In this reference condition, we assume the scheduled buffer for flight f remains unchanged from year y to $y+1$. This is used to examine how much observed delay will increase (or decrease) if buffer time is fixed. Then, all the expected changes in true arrival delay will be added to the observed arrival delay. Let α_f denote the reference change rate of observed arrival delay for flight f from year y to $y+1$, then we have:

$$\Delta TAD_f = OAD_f^y \alpha_f \quad (8)$$

b) **Reference 2: Fix delay.** In this reference condition, we aim to evaluate how much the scheduled buffer time should be adjusted if airlines desire to maintain the same level of observed arrival delay in year $y+1$, i.e. delay is fixed. In this case, all the expected changes in true arrival delay will be added to the scheduled buffer. Let β_f denote the adjustment rate of scheduled buffer for flight f from year y to $y+1$ in this reference condition, then we have:

$$\Delta TAD_f = SFB_f^y \beta_f \quad (9)$$

B. Trade-off Equation

Leveraging the numerical relationship among the 4 change rates, we define a unified equation to capture the trade-off between scheduled buffer and observed arrival delay in schedule adjustment. Let the right-hand sides of equations (8) and (9) divide the right-hand side of equation (7). Since the right-hand sides of equations (8) and (9) are equal, the expression can be reformulated into the following equation:

$$\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} + \frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f} = 1 \quad (10)$$

Note that this equation is valid only when $\Delta TAD_f \neq 0$. Otherwise, when $\Delta TAD_f = 0$, if the airlines would like to adjust the scheduled buffer, the relationship could be as follows: $\frac{\omega_f}{\nu_f} = -\frac{OAD_f^y}{SFB_f^y}$. However, in most cases, they can maintain the same scheduled time, and then $\omega_f = \nu_f = 0$. Here, we only investigate the situation when $\Delta TAD_f \neq 0$ as this is more challenging for decision-making.

In equation (10), the first part $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ represents the portion of the expected change in true arrival delay (ΔTAD_f) that the airlines want to be observed in operation. The second part $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$ represents the portion of ΔTAD_f that the airlines want to be hidden in the schedule by adding buffer time. Table I summarizes the notations and their corresponding descriptions in the adjustment trade-off model.

TABLE I. Descriptions of notations in buffer adjustment trade-off model.

Notation	Description
SFB_f^y	scheduled buffer for flight f in year y
OAD_f^y	observed arrival delay for flight f in year y
TAD_f^y	true arrival delay for flight f in year y
ΔTAD_f	change of true arrival delay for flight f from year y to $y+1$
ν_f	change rate of observed arrival delay for flight f from year y to $y+1$
ω_f	adjustment rate of scheduled buffer for flight f from year y to $y+1$
α_f	change rate of observed arrival delay for flight f from year y to $y+1$ if scheduled buffer is fixed
β_f	adjustment rate of scheduled buffer for flight f from year y to $y+1$ if no change in observed arrival delay is desired
$\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$	the fraction of ΔTAD_f that is to be observed for flight f in year $y+1$
$\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$	the fraction of ΔTAD_f that is to be hidden in schedule buffer for flight f in year $y+1$
$\frac{\alpha_f}{\beta_f}$	trade-off rate, i.e. how much of ω_f must increase to compensate for one unit decrease in ν_f for flight f in $y+1$

C. Buffer Time Adjustment Scenarios and Effectiveness

By leveraging equation (10) and the quantitative relationships among the four rates ν_f , ω_f , α_f and β_f , we define 12 distinct buffer adjustment scenarios, each corresponding to different operational outcomes. The two reference conditions introduced earlier serve as benchmarks to assess the effectiveness of buffer adjustment strategies. Specifically, by comparing ν_f and α_f , as well as ω_f and β_f , we evaluate whether the buffer adjustment successfully offsets flight delays. This approach enables a systematic analysis of how different adjustment strategies influence operational performance.

Figure 2 illustrates the four quadrants and their corresponding value ranges for ω_f and ν_f . Depending on the values of ΔTAD_f and OAD_f^y , each quadrant reflects different operational outcomes.

Figure 2: Four quadrants and the corresponding value ranges for ω_f and ν_f .

Buffer time adjustment scenarios are defined based on

the values of $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$, $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$, ΔTAD_f , and OAD_f^y , where $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ and $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$ have three segmented ranges, ΔTAD_f and OAD_f^y each has two ranges (positive and negative). In total, there are 12 combinations. Table II summarizes the twelve distinct scenarios and their interpretations. The segmented ranges of $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ and $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$ determine three clusters of scenarios with different effectiveness:

- a) **Appropriate buffer adjustment:** $0 < \frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} < 1$ and $0 < \frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f} < 1$. Scenarios 1-4 are in this cluster. Buffer adjustments offset the changes in observed delay appropriately.
- b) **Excessive buffer adjustment:** $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} < 0$ and $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f} > 1$. Scenarios 5-8 are in this cluster. The buffer time increase or decrease exceeds the amount required to offset the changes in true delay.
- c) **Misaligned buffer adjustment:** $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} > 1$ and $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f} < 0$. Scenarios 9-12 are in this cluster. Reducing buffer when an increase is needed or increasing buffer when a reduction is needed, leading to more delays and early arrivals, respectively.

Among these 12 scenarios, the following scenarios are not effective in terms of offsetting delays and should be avoided:

- Scenario 5: The excessive buffer increase is only reasonable when the observed delay in year y is high. However, if $\nu_f < -1$, the buffer is increased too much and leads to early arrivals.
- Scenario 6: The excessive buffer increase leads to more severe early arrivals.
- Scenario 7: The reference condition $\alpha_f < 0$ indicates that observed delays will decrease if there is no change to the buffer. However, the $\nu_f > 0$ and $\omega_f < \beta_f < 0$ illustrate that the excessive buffer decrease results in increased delay instead.
- Scenario 8: The excessive buffer decrease is only reasonable when the buffer time in year y is high. However, if $\nu_f < -1$, the buffer is decreased too much and leads to late arrivals.
- Scenario 9: Buffer is reduced when an increase is required, leading to increased observed delay.
- Scenario 10: The reduced buffer is only reasonable when the buffer time in year y is high. However, if $\nu_f < -1$, the buffer is reduced too much and results in late arrivals.
- Scenario 11: The increased buffer is only reasonable when the observed delay in year y is high. However, if $\nu_f < -1$, the buffer is increased too much and leads to early arrivals.
- Scenario 12: Buffer is reduced when an increase is required, leading to more severe early arrivals.

In addition to the effectiveness of buffer adjustments, Scenarios 1, 5, and 9 should require attention, where late-arriving flights will experience increasing true arrival delays in the next year. This implies that the operational environment for these flights will continue to deteriorate. On the contrary, scenarios 4, 8, and 12 represent that the early-arriving flights will experience a reduction in true arrival delay, i.e., a better operational environment in the next year. Airlines can utilize these scenarios to check

whether they adjust scheduled buffer time appropriately.

D. Discuss the Application and Advantages in Schedule Adjustment Decision-making

Airlines can apply the proposed approach to support their schedule adjustment decision-making according to their own on-time performance target and business strategy. The procedure can be as follows:

- Predict true arrival delay in next year TAD_f^{y+1} .
- Calculate changes in true arrival delay ΔTAD_f .
- Calculate reference change rate α and β by fixing buffer or observed delay.
- Determine next year's desired arrival delay and obtain ν .
- Get adjustment rate of scheduled buffer ω by plugging in other variables in equation (10).

In this process, the decision variables in schedule adjustment are ν_f and ω_f , while α_f and β_f can be considered as known coefficients for each estimated ΔTAD_f . To apply this approach in buffer time adjustment, true arrival delay in the next year should be predicted. Recently, a series of machine learning-based methods have been proposed to predict flight delay, covering prediction horizons ranging from several hours to several months in advance [13]. While existing research primarily focuses on predicting observed delays, the underlying methodologies can be adapted to true arrival delay prediction.

Leveraging the proposed approach, this schedule adjustment procedure has several advantages:

- a) **Avoid dynamic endogeneity in predictive modeling:** In the literature, approaches for predicting SBT or buffer time adjustment in year $t+1$ typically rely on historical flight performance data, such as observed arrival delays and OTP from year t or earlier. However, these performance metrics themselves depend on the SBT previously set in year t . Therefore, it introduces a dynamic endogeneity issue. This problem occurs when the current values of a study's independent variables are affected by the past values of the dependent variables, which can lead to biased estimates [14]. In contrast, the above-mentioned procedure relies on the prediction of TAD_f^{y+1} . The true arrival delay is not affected by scheduled buffer time. As a measure of the additional delay beyond the UBT, it primarily depends on external factors within NAS, reflecting only changes in the operating environment.
- b) **Evaluate effectiveness without complex simulation:** The equation (10) enables a quick estimation of the observed delay and on-time performance under each buffer strategy without cumbersome simulations. The 12 adjustment scenarios provide a convenient tool for assessing the effectiveness of decisions.
- c) **Adapt to significant operational changes:** Unlike previous econometric models, our approach does not rely on estimating coefficients from historical data. The existing models in the literature may provide biased results if the distributions of variables shift. Our approach is adaptable to significant changes in the operating environment

TABLE II. Flights located in different quadrants and the corresponding interpretations in operations.

Scenario	Segmented Ranges	ΔTAD_f	OAD_f^y	ν_f	ω_f	Interpretation	Quadrant
1	$0 < \frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} < 1$ $0 < \frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f} < 1$	> 0	> 0	$0 < \nu_f < \alpha_f$	$0 < \omega_f < \beta_f$	Both buffer and delay increase. Increasing buffer time mitigates the extent of delay increase.	I
2			< 0	$\alpha_f < \nu_f < 0$			II
3		< 0	> 0	$\alpha_f < \nu_f < 0$	$\beta_f < \omega_f < 0$	Both buffer and delay decrease. The buffer time reduction mitigates the extent of delay reduction.	III
4			< 0	$0 < \nu_f < \alpha_f$			IV
5	$\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} < 0$ $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f} > 1$	> 0	> 0	$\nu_f < 0 < \alpha_f$	$0 < \beta_f < \omega_f$	Buffer increases while delay decreases. The increase in buffer time exceeds the amount required to offset the true delay increase.	II
6			< 0	$\alpha_f < 0 < \nu_f$			I
7		< 0	> 0	$\alpha_f < 0 < \nu_f$	$\omega_f < \beta_f < 0$	Buffer decreases while delay increases. The buffer decrease exceeds the necessary level, resulting in an increase in delay.	IV
8			< 0	$\nu_f < 0 < \alpha_f$			III
9	$\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} > 1$ $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f} < 0$	> 0	> 0	$0 < \alpha_f < \nu_f$	$\omega_f < 0 < \beta_f$	Buffer decrease while delay increase. A reduction in buffer time, when an increase is required, leads to increased delay.	IV
10			< 0	$\nu_f < \alpha_f < 0$			III
11		< 0	> 0	$\nu_f < \alpha_f < 0$	$\beta_f < 0 < \omega_f$	Buffer increase while delay decrease. The increase in buffer time, when a reduction is required, leads to more severe early arrivals.	II
12			< 0	$0 < \alpha_f < \nu_f$			I

(reflected in true arrival delay), such as improvements contributed by NEXTGEN, and thus allows the model to capture how airlines adjust their strategies in response to evolving conditions.

We further investigate how the changes in the true arrival delay of next year will affect the decision-making in theory. According to equations (8) and (9), the predicted value of true arrival delay in next year will affect ΔTAD_f , and thus influence the values of α_f and β_f . Given the scheduled buffer and observed delay in year y , each value of ΔTAD_f will determine a pair of coefficients α_f and β_f . Then, the relationship between ν_f and ω_f can be illustrated using Figure 3. Each point on the line represents one trade-off solution of schedule buffer and observed delay adjustment, i.e., ν_f and ω_f under the same ΔTAD_f . It is the airline's strategy to determine which solution will be used to adjust next year's scheduled time. For this purpose, a cost function based on ω_f and ν_f can be defined at first. The optimal choices will be those that can minimize the cost function. The intercepts on two axes are the α_f and β_f under two reference conditions.

Figure 3: Relationship between adjustment rate of buffer ν_f and change rate of delay ω_f for flight f (for $\omega_f > 0, \nu_f > 0$).

The slope of the line indicates the “rate of trade-off” between scheduled buffer times and observed arrival delays. $-\frac{\beta_f}{\alpha_f}$ represents how much the change rate of delay ν_f will decrease due to one unit increase in buffer adjustment rate ω_f . On the other hand, $-\frac{\alpha_f}{\beta_f}$ indicates how much buffer the adjustment

rate ω_f must increase to compensate for one unit decrease in ν_f for flight f when setting schedule in year $y + 1$.

Note that while the model in this section is at the individual flight level, it can also be extended to the airline or market level for macroscopic analysis. For this purpose, the schedule buffer, observed arrival delay, and true arrival delay should be replaced by the weighted metrics defined in each market.

IV. EMPIRICAL STUDY RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents an empirical study employing the proposed methods, utilizing real-world schedule data and operational data. The objectives are to uncover common and distinctive schedule adjustment practices across different airlines and identify the contributing factors that lead to ineffective buffer adjustments.

A. Data Source

The Bureau of Transportation Statistics (BTS) Airline On-Time Performance Database is employed in this study. This database provides detailed information for each scheduled domestic flight operated by major carriers. The recorded information includes origin, destination, airline, scheduled departure time (STD), scheduled arrival time (STA), actual departure time (ATD), actual arrival time (ATA), gate out, wheels off, wheels on, and gate in (OOOI) times, and cancellation state of each individual flight. The data from January 2022 to December 2023 is used for the case study. Five major airlines in the U.S. are selected: Delta Airlines (DL), American Airlines (AA), United Airlines (UA), Southwest Airlines (WN) and JetBlue (B6). The former 3 airlines are FSCs with hub-and-spoke network structures, while Southwest and Jetblue are LCCs with point-to-point network structures. The domestic market shares of these 5 airlines are 17.8%, 17.5%, 17.3%, 15.9%, and 4.7%. We exclude weekend flights, cancelled and diverted flights, as well as flights with origin or destination in Alaska, Hawaii, and other overseas territories. Then, the required variables are calculated by following the methodology outlined earlier and are utilized in the analysis presented in this section. After processing, the airlines have 31465 (AA), 23913 (UA), 25297 (DL), 29709 (WN), and 5771 (B6) HFGs.

B. Results of Empirical Study

Following the procedures outlined in Section III, the variables presented in Table I are derived and subsequently employed in the empirical analysis. As discussed in the methodology section, our interest lies in cases where $\Delta TAD_f \neq 0$. For calculation purposes, we also exclude the data with $OAD_f^y = 0$. Then, the filtered data retains 80% - 85% of the HFGs for each airline.

We first assess the overall effectiveness of buffer adjustment by examining the distribution of individual flights across the 12 buffer adjustment scenarios illustrated in Table II. As depicted in Figure 4, the distribution of historical flights across different scenarios is not uniform. Scenarios 6, 7, 9, 12, and $\nu_f < -1$ in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 correspond to ineffective buffer time adjustment decisions that should be avoided. Results indicate that 38.8% (AA), 31.6% (UA),

33.7% (DL), 36.3% (WN), and 36.5% (B6) of flights fall into the ineffective categories. From a retrospective perspective, this highlights considerable inefficiencies in the buffer time setting among these airlines. It should be noted that based on the current practice, the selected airlines do not consider variations of true delay in the next year when they adjust schedules. The flights located in the ineffective scenarios are due to the lack of correct assumptions of future delay. Therefore, from a different standpoint, these large portions of ineffective flights imply the potential improvement in schedule adjustments if airlines can consider future delay variations.

Scenarios 6 and 12 correspond to inappropriate increases in buffer time, either due to excessive increase or increases when reductions are warranted. It is evident that the 3 FSC airlines have a higher proportion of flights falling into this category, particularly in the case of DL. This suggests that these airlines tend to set longer buffer time in the schedule. A reason is that FSC airlines put a higher weight on the cost of late arrivals than do LCCs [15]. However, evidence shows that such practice is not always effective. The flights in the scenario 1,5, and 9 are less frequent but require the most attention. These scenarios include late-arriving flights that will experience increased true arrival delay in the following year. This implies that the operational environment for these flights will continue to deteriorate. According to the empirical results, WN and B6 have more such flights compared with AA, UA and DL.

Figure 4: Percentage of flights in the 12 scenarios (Note: Scenarios 6, 7, 9, 12, and $\nu_f < -1$ in scenarios 5, 8, 10 and 11 correspond to ineffective buffer time adjustment.)

We then investigate the flights located in scenarios 1-4, i.e., $0 < \frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} < 1$, representing the appropriate scheduled buffer adjustment choices. In Figure 5, each point represents a trade-off choice for an HFG. The color of the points represents the value of ΔTAD_f , and the shape of the points represents

whether the OAD_f^y is positive or negative. The percentages of flights located in four quadrants are also shown respectively.

As illustrated in Figure 5, these five airlines share several common patterns. First, compared with $\Delta TAD_f < 0$, the adjustment rate of buffer (ω_f) under $\Delta TAD_f > 0$ is relatively larger, indicating that buffer adjustment is more sensitive to true delay increase than decrease. In addition, it can be observed that the range of adjustment rate of scheduled buffer time is much smaller than the range of change rate of observed delay. It assumes a practice that scheduled buffer time is not adjusted too much across years. On the contrary, the variation in delay is more significant. An interesting observation is that the late-arriving flights (in quadrants I and III) predominantly experience a decrease in ΔTAD_f (blue points), whereas most early-arriving flights (in quadrants II and IV) exhibit an increase in ΔTAD_f (red points). This may result in the oscillation of buffer time and observed delay across years. Further investigation may be needed to understand this phenomenon. While some trends are consistent, differences in patterns are also evident among the airlines. One notable difference may be related to the airline's FSC or LCC classification. First, the three FSC airlines AA, UA, and DL have more data located in quadrants II and IV, indicating that these airlines have more early arrivals (84.5%-94.5%), compared with the two LCC airlines WN and B6 (52.4%-54.6%). Among the three FSC airlines, DL has the most frequent early arrivals. This is consistent with our early findings that DL prefers to set long SBT to absorb delays [7] and improve network resilience [16].

We then investigate the trade-off between buffer time and arrival delay. Figure 6 compares the distribution of $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ and $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$ for each airline. As introduced in the methodology section, $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ represents the fraction of ΔTAD_f that is to be observed for flight f in year $y + 1$, while $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$ represents the fraction of ΔTAD_f that is to be hidden in schedule buffer for flight f in year $y + 1$. As depicted in Figure 6, the value of $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ is generally larger than $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$. It implies that these five airlines favor allowing more ΔTAD_f to manifest in operations rather than concealing them within their schedules. Compared with others, DL has a larger value of $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$, suggesting that DL "hides" more true delay in the scheduled buffer. Additionally, the two LCC airlines WN and B6 have smaller $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$, which means that less fraction of ΔTAD_f is added to the buffer. These two airlines operate in the point-to-point network structure with few connecting flights. Thus, they are less motivated to increase scheduled buffer time to mitigate the effects of delay propagation.

Drawing from the above findings, the company's adjustments to the scheduled buffer appear relatively limited, suggesting a preference for exposing the ΔTAD_f within the observed arrival delay. This raises the question of whether the company tends to adopt a strategy of keeping the buffer time unchanged. To address this, we compare the actual adjustment rate ν_f and ω_f with their corresponding reference adjustment rate α_f and β_f . The Concordance Correlation Coefficient is applied to measure the agreement between pairs of variables. Unlike Pearson's correlation, which only measures linear

association, CCC evaluates how well two sets of data match in both trend and magnitude. For two variables x and y , their Concordance Correlation Coefficient ρ_c can be calculated as:

$$\rho_c = \frac{2\rho\sigma_x\sigma_y}{\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + (\mu_x - \mu_y)^2} \quad (11)$$

Where ρ is the Pearson correlation coefficient between the two variables, μ_x and μ_y are their mean values, and σ_x and σ_y are their standard deviations. The CCC value ranges from -1 to 1 , with perfect agreement at 1 . Table III shows the ρ_c of two pairs of variables for each airline. The Concordance

TABLE III. Concordance Correlation Coefficient for ν_f , α_f and ω_f , β_f .

Airlines	$\rho_c(\nu_f, \alpha_f)$	$\rho_c(\omega_f, \beta_f)$
AA	0.871	0.562
UA	0.864	0.572
DL	0.842	0.675
WN	0.871	0.432
B6	0.864	0.515

Correlation Coefficients for ν_f and α_f are about 0.85-0.87, while the Concordance Correlation Coefficients for ω_f and β_f are around 0.43-0.67. It indicates that the actual change rate of observed delay aligns more closely with the "Fix buffer" reference condition. In other words, airlines tend to avoid making significant adjustments to scheduled buffer time. Kang and Hansen developed discrete choice models to study the SBT adjustment in U.S. airlines using 2011-2012 historical data [2]. Similar "sticky" SBT adjustment behaviors are also revealed in their study. Combining the observations from Figure 5 and Figure 6, it can be inferred that such "sticky" buffer time setting strategy demonstrates limited capacity to facilitate the company's adaptation to system environment changes and mitigate adverse effects on on-time performance.

C. Driving Factors of Ineffective Buffer Adjustments

The objective of this analysis is to examine the driving factors behind ineffective buffer adjustments and identify the characteristics of the affected flights. We categorize buffer adjustment scenarios into three classes in terms of effectiveness, as introduced in the methodology section: **Class-1**: appropriate buffer adjustment, **Class-2**: excessive buffer adjustment, and **Class-3**: misaligned buffer adjustment. The Multinomial Logit (MNL) model [17] is applied to relate contributing factors to the three classes. We consider a range of factors, i.e., explanatory variables, to assess their impact on decision-making. These variables are summarized in Table IV. We separately consider the positive and negative ΔTAD_f since their expected adjustments of buffers are in different directions. Also, we use airline-specific models as each airline has its own scheduling strategy. The MNL models are estimated using the Maximum Likelihood Estimation. The estimation results are presented in Table V and Table VI, where Class-1: appropriate buffer adjustment serves as the reference category for comparison. Due to space constraints,

Figure 5: Visualization of ω_f and ν_f for the range $0 < \frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} < 1$ with percentages of flights in each quadrant.

Figure 6: Distributions of $\frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f}$ and $\frac{\omega_f}{\beta_f}$ across airlines for the range $0 < \frac{\nu_f}{\alpha_f} < 1$.

we report here only the estimation results for three airline-specific models. However, the findings are discussed based on the results of all five airlines.

Combining the results from the 2 tables, we identify that the flights with the following attributes are more likely to undergo ineffective buffer adjustments (Class-2 and Class-3):

- **Low frequency:** The estimation values of variable "frequency" for all airlines in both tables are all negative. It suggests that flights with high frequencies are less likely to be categorized as ineffective. A possible reason is that airlines pay more attention to high-frequency flights,

TABLE IV. Explanatory Variables Description in Multinomial Logit Model

Notation	Description	Type
UBT	Unimpeded block time for flight f in year $y + 1$.	Continuous
FQ	Frequency of flight f in year $y + 1$, i.e., number of flights in each HFG	Continuous.
DT_k	Departure time window as defined in Section II-A. $k \in \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. 1 if the departure time is within window k , 0 otherwise.	Dummy
Q_i	Quarter of the year. $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$. 1 if the quarter is i , 0 otherwise.	Dummy
OH	1 if a flight's origin airport is the hub of the airlines, 0 otherwise	Dummy
DH	1 if a flight's destination airport is the hub of the airlines, 0 otherwise	Dummy
ΔTAD_f	Change of true arrival delay for flight f from year y to $y + 1$	Continuous
OAD_f^y	Observed arrival delay for flight f in year y	Continuous

which are supposed to be more important.

- **Small absolute value of ΔTAD_f :** The negative values in Table V and positive values in Table VI of this variable indicate that flights with small changes in true arrival delay are more likely to have ineffective buffer adjustments. While these flights seem less critical than high delay-variation flights, neglecting them can lead to substantial inefficiencies and increased costs.
- **Long UBT:** In Table VI, the positive estimation values for Class-2 and negative estimation values for Class-3 indicate that when $\Delta TAD_f < 0$, flights with long UBT are more likely to have excessive buffer decrease, but less likely to have buffer adjusted in the wrong direction.

TABLE V. Multinomial Logit Model Estimation Results for $\Delta TAD_f > 0$.

Variables	Estimation					
	UA		DL		WN	
	Class-2	Class-3	Class-2	Class-3	Class-2	Class-3
<i>const</i>	1.286**	-0.488**	2.560**	-1.703**	2.105**	-0.991**
<i>UBT</i>	0.004**	-0.002**	0.001*	0.003**	0.006**	0.002**
<i>FQ</i>	-0.002**	-0.003**	-0.005**	-0.004**	-0.003**	-0.002**
<i>DT₂</i>	-0.307**	0.110*	-0.471**	0.341**	-0.966**	0.658**
<i>DT₃</i>	-0.748**	0.653**	-0.684**	0.514**	-0.518**	1.286**
<i>DT₄</i>	-0.607**	0.535**	-1.026**	0.780**	-1.525**	1.380**
<i>DT₅</i>	-0.163	0.044	-0.368**	0.443**	0.281*	0.610**
<i>Q₂</i>	0.375**	-0.051	-0.303**	-0.081	-0.973**	0.300**
<i>Q₃</i>	0.247*	-0.270**	-0.052	-0.310**	-1.500**	0.196**
<i>Q₄</i>	1.148**	-1.298**	0.881**	-0.903**	-0.227*	-0.661**
<i>OH</i>	-0.366**	0.222*	-0.009	0.399**	-0.708**	0.378**
<i>DH</i>	0.157	-0.016	0.426**	0.066	0.265*	-0.166**
ΔTAD_f	-0.221**	-0.086**	-0.185**	-0.162**	-0.272**	-0.075**
OAD_f^y	0.132**	-0.153**	0.141**	-0.167**	0.108**	-0.128**
R_{McF}^2	0.174		0.171		0.167	

** Significant at 0.01, * Significant at 0.05.

TABLE VI. Multinomial Logit Model Estimation Results for $\Delta TAD_f < 0$.

Variables	Estimation					
	UA		DL		WN	
	Class-2	Class-3	Class-2	Class-3	Class-2	Class-3
<i>const</i>	-0.909**	2.083**	-1.806**	2.607**	-1.865**	2.741**
<i>UBT</i>	0.001	-0.001	0.003**	-0.001*	0.012**	-0.003**
<i>FQ</i>	-0.002*	-0.003**	-0.002*	-0.004**	-0.002*	-0.001
<i>DT₂</i>	0.200*	-0.384**	0.408**	-0.412**	0.860**	-0.873**
<i>DT₃</i>	0.568**	-0.761**	0.359**	-0.269**	1.361**	-1.786**
<i>DT₄</i>	0.313**	-0.324**	0.309**	-0.414**	1.277**	-1.775**
<i>DT₅</i>	-0.154	-0.113	0.327**	-0.288**	-0.493**	0.172**
<i>Q₂</i>	-0.145	0.134	-0.600**	0.121	0.374**	-0.954**
<i>Q₃</i>	-0.305**	0.171*	-0.489**	0.071	0.266*	-1.530**
<i>Q₄</i>	-1.105**	1.127**	-1.351**	0.696**	-0.470**	-0.295**
<i>OH</i>	0.245	-0.539**	0.380**	0.061	0.251**	-0.583**
<i>DH</i>	-0.130	0.234*	-0.033	0.336	-0.184*	0.109*
ΔTAD_f	0.170**	0.182**	0.181**	0.200**	0.206**	0.219**
OAD_f^y	-0.197**	0.167**	-0.221**	0.181**	-0.236**	0.218**
R_{McF}^2	0.245		0.205		0.325	

** Significant at 0.01, * Significant at 0.05.

Similarly, positive values in Table V also suggest that flights with long UBT are more likely to have excessive buffer increase when $\Delta TAD_f > 0$. A possible reason is that airlines may adjust their schedule in terms of a percentile of the historical block time [6]. Long UBTs will thus result in significant adjustments.

These findings highlight that rather than employing the same strategy for all flights, tailored strategies should be developed for the 3 types of flights mentioned above.

The results also suggest other buffer adjustment strategies. First, compared with the departure time window of 08 : 00–11 : 59, all airlines prefer to decrease buffer times for flights with departure time windows later in the day. Second, all airlines, except American Airlines (AA), tend to reduce buffers for flights departing from hub airports and increase buffers for those arriving at hub airports. Third, the large observed delay in year y leads to an increasing buffer, and

small observed delay or early arrivals in year y leads to buffer reduction, which is consistent with intuition.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, we develop an analytical approach to analyze airlines' scheduled buffer time adjustment strategies. Specifically, we focus on the trade-off between buffer time and the arrival delay, as well as the effectiveness of buffer adjustments. Leveraging flight time decomposition, we interpreted this trade-off behavior as a decision regarding how much of the delay is hidden within the schedule and how much is exposed in the observed performance. We integrate the changes in buffer and arrival delay into one equation to quantitatively capture the trade-off relationship between them. Based on this model, 12 buffer adjustment scenarios with operational interpretations are defined, which provides a tool to analyze the effectiveness of buffer adjustment decisions. The proposed model is applied to conduct an empirical study on five U.S. airlines. Results suggest that there are considerable inefficiencies in the buffer time setting among these airlines. For about 31%-38% of the flights in selected airlines, their buffer adjustments cannot account for the delay changes from a retrospective view. Since airlines' current strategies primarily focus on maintaining certain block time reliability and adjusting schedules based on past year OTP, our results also highlight the potential improvement in schedule adjustments if airlines can consider future delay variations and have a reliable forecast. Additionally, it demonstrates that buffer adjustment is more sensitive to true delay increases than decreases. We also find that airlines tend to avoid making significant adjustments to scheduled buffer time, and such a strategy is not efficient in adapting to system environment changes. Finally, we apply the Multinomial Logit model to examine the driving factors and characteristics behind ineffective buffer adjustments. Results show that attention and tailored adjustment strategies are needed for flights with low frequency, small true delay variation, and long flight time to enhance effectiveness. Based on the proposed approach, the analysis of open-source real-world data supports comprehensive evaluation of schedule-setting strategies for airlines, their partners, and competitors, and informs potential improvements. Beyond retrospective analysis, the method offers a new perspective for guiding future strategy design and, when combined with delay prediction models, can support more effective buffer settings. This research contributes to the literature by providing both theoretical insights and practical tools to enhance airline scheduling strategies.

In future work, we will incorporate data spanning multiple years, with a particular focus on periods preceding, during, and following the COVID-19 pandemic. This will allow us to examine whether and how the buffer-setting strategy changed in response to the system-wide disruptions with long-term uncertainties. A more sophisticated version of the model could be developed in future work by incorporating richer information, such as airline fleets and other relevant factors. The proposed approach can also be employed to analyze the airlines' strategy in other countries and regions. For

example, China and Europe, where the IATA slot coordination process is widely implemented, can serve as valuable comparators. The proposed approach can be applied under the IATA slot coordination framework with minimal limitations. Although overall flexibility in schedule adjustment is reduced, airlines can still make modifications within their allocated slot windows, and such adjustment behaviors remain analyzable using the proposed method. Understanding how slot coordination influences scheduling decisions represents an interesting direction for future research. It would also be insightful to explore the extent to which central planners in a predominantly centrally controlled market, such as China, can grant flexibility to air carriers to achieve enhanced system operational performance.

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